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TESTING THE PERFORMANCE, ADEQUACY, AND APPLICABILITY OF AN ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENT MODEL FOR PEDIATRIC PNEUMONIA DIAGNOSIS

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ABSTRACT

Community-acquired Pneumonia (CAP) is the most common infectious disease in childhood. Deep learning models have achieved promising results in X-ray interpretation and diagnosis. However, the usual validation workflow of these models could be extended. Usually, the performance of a model is tested considering a perfect ground truth (there are no discrepancies in the labels), which is unrealistic when dealing with medical diagnosis. In addition, it is often left aside to check whether the model is useful for clinicians (applicability) and whether its predictions are in line with the logic followed by experts (adequacy). This study proposes an extended workflow where the performance of an already published convolutional neural network (CNN) support decision tool (SDT) is tested taking into account the above considerations. Specifically, to test the performance of the model with an imperfect ground truth an extension of the two-test Bayesian Latent-Class model (BLCA) was used. Moreover, the clinical characteristics of the patients were compared accordingly. In addition, the adequacy and applicability of the SDT were assessed using explainable artificial intelligence (XAI) techniques. The former was tested by asking two senior physicians the agreement rate with the SDT, and the latter by asking three medical residents before and after using the SDT. In both cases, the agreement between experts was calculated using the kappa index. The panel of experts labeled the CRXs into consolidation (124/176, 70.4%) and no-consolidation/other infiltrates (52/176, 29.5%). Discrepancies were found between the model and the panel of experts in 31/176 (17.6%) CRXs with a kappa index of 0.6. The sensitivity and specificity reached a median of 90.9 and 77.7 respectively. The senior physicians reported a high agreement rate (70%) with the system in identifying logical consolidation patterns. Finally, the three medical residents reached a higher agreement using SDT than alone (0.66 ± 0.1 vs. 0.75 ± 0.2).

Keywords Chest X-Ray · CNNs · Deep-Learning · Pediatrics · Pneumonia

1 Introduction

Community-acquired Pneumonia (CAP) is the most common infectious disease in childhood. Establishing CAP etiology can often be challenging due to the time-consuming process of the microbiology diagnosis. Given the heterogeneity of the symptoms and uncertain sensitivity or specificity of physical examination, physicians often rely on radiographic findings [1]. However, the process of reading Chest X-ray (CXR) images can be subjective or inaccurate since the interpretation depends on the expertise. The CXRs are classified into: normal, consolidation, which corresponds to alveolar pneumonia, and non-consolidation/other infiltrates corresponding to non-alveolar pneumonia [2]. The consolidation pattern in the CXRs is associated with bacterial pneumonia and the other infiltrates are likely associated with viral pneumonia. This pattern in the CXRs is followed by an empirical decision of antibiotics prescription [2] which often results in an over-treatment with antibiotics reinforcing the need for better tools to find an appropriate diagnosis [3].

Researchers have proposed several computer algorithms to analyze CXR images [4, 5]. Deep Learning has demonstrated high performance in image interpretation and diagnosis [6, 7]. Specifically, Convolutional Neural Network (CNNs) [8, 9], are inspired by the overall learning process of the visual cortex and are commonly used in the field of computer vision. Several decision-support tools (SDT) that include this technology have been developed to assist physicians in making decisions [10, 11]. However, a recent systematic review enhances the problem that despite recent improvements in the quality of AI products and AI applications in radiology, none of the thoracic AI systems is specifically designed for the pediatric population [12].

Although these computer-aided classification systems provide an extensive experimental evaluation by several radiologist experts [10, 11, 13, 14], a radiologist and/or expert pediatrician reporting for every image is not always possible due to the routine workload or the lack of experienced staff in low resources areas. In addition, most of the studies used expert readings as gold standards or ground truth to train and test their performance [10, 11, 13, 14]. This assumes that the gold standard is perfect (100% sensitive and specific). However, a high intra and inter-observer variability has been reported [15, 16]. If the error rates of a gold standard are ignored during the evaluation of new diagnostic tests or support-decision systems, the accuracy of new tests or systems can be underestimated [17–19]. To overcome this pitfall, the use of Bayesian latent class models (BLCA) was proposed as a method to estimate the accuracy of diagnostic tests when the accuracy of the gold standard is unknown [20].

In addition, studies usually evaluate their models without analyzing their applicability and adequacy, i.e., without ensuring that the model would be usable by end-users and can identify logical medical patterns [10, 21]. Doing this is of vital importance in fields like medicine and health care. Especially when using Deep Learning because is difficult for

Figure 1: Workload presented in this study

humans to understand how the system has reached a particular conclusion (this phenomenon is called the “Blackbox syndrome”). In response to this problem, the field of Explainable Artificial Intelligence (XAI) was born [22–24]. The use of XAI allows evaluating a model beyond common quantitative analysis increasing the trust between humans and AI. Assessing whether the patterns found by a ML model are in line with the logic followed by senior physicians or if these same patterns are of use for less experienced ones, is mandatory for any model that aims to be included in the clinical routines.

The STD tool evaluated in this work has been previously trained and validated by some members of the group following the standard quantitative procedure [25]. Several experiments, including transfer learning, were performed to find the best architecture using public (5856 CXRs) and private (950 CXRs) datasets. Due to the good results obtained by the aforementioned model, this study aims to further test the performance, applicability, and adequacy of the CXRs CNN ensemble system tool (SDT) following the above considerations and using an independent pediatric CXRs set (Figure 1).

The main contribution of the article can be summarized as follows:

- A STD specifically tailored to pediatric CAP.
- High throughput bayesian methodology to assess the performance when the accuracy of the gold standard is unknown.
- Additional testing of the adequacy and applicability of the tool using XAI techniques together with physicians feedback.

2 Materials and methods

2.1 Study population

To test the performance of the SDT, a total of 190 pediatric CXRs images were collected from the observational multi-center prospective cohort studies VALSDANCE and PCAPE [2, 26]. Eligible participants were children and adolescents from 1 month to 17 years hospitalized with CAP. The interpretation of the CXRs was performed following the standards of the “WHO Vaccine Trial Investigators Radiology Working Group” [2] classifying the CXRs images

in consolidation or other infiltrates. A panel of experts composed of two pediatricians (AT and EO) interpreted the CXRs.

For the second objective which aims to evaluate the adequacy of the system, a subset of 40/190 of the above pediatric CXRs images labeled as consolidation from both SDT and the experts were shown to two independent senior pediatricians (CM and PR) to test if the consolidation pattern identified by the SDT was correct.

Finally, to evaluate the applicability of the system, an independent subset of 40 pediatric CXRs images provided by Ben-Gurion University (Israel) were randomly selected from the training set of this CNN algorithm. These CRXs images were labeled by two senior pediatricians (RD y DG) and a radiologist from Ben-Gurion University (Israel). The experts also had access to lateral radiographs of the patients to increase the precision of the labeling of each case. The CXR reading project was approved by the Soroka University Ethics Committee (Number 3075).

This study was approved by the Ethics Board of coordinating hospitals (codes Hospital Infanta Sofía (Madrid, Spain) 320/11 and Hospital 12 Octubre (Madrid, Spain) 17/311).

An extensive microbiological workup was performed. All the laboratory methods were described in Supplementary Material appendix A.

The SDT used in this study has already been designed and validated by members of our team following the standard procedure. In Supplementary Material appendix B, there is a summary of the experiments and the results obtained. For a detailed description of the training procedure, the architecture of the ensemble model, and its performance we refer the reader to the original paper [25].

2.2 Evaluation

The performance of the model was estimated using extensions of the two-test, two BLCA [27] implemented in a simplified interface application [19]. We divide the overall sample into two subpopulations according to age. This is because BLCA needs to estimate true disease prevalence, and a 2x2 summary table of two diagnostic tests applied to one population does not provide enough data for this calculation [20, 28]. In the event that two diagnostic tests were applied together to one population, it is possible to divide a single population data set into multiple population data sets with different prevalences based on specific variables [29]. Non-informative prior distribution was used for all parameter estimations. The model was set with 2 Markov chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) chains, 5000 burn-in iterations, 25000 total iterations, and 10 thinning intervals. The convergence was checked using tracing plots and the fitness of the model was checked through observed and predicted frequencies comparison. To assess the probability of observed frequencies, the dataset was replicated 20000 times and selected only 2000 times (thin=10). To evaluate the performance of the model we used confusion matrices to assess sensitivity, specificity, false-positive rate, true positive rate, and the area under the operating curve (AUC). We also provided the results for conventional methods where the gold standard was considered 100% sensible and specific.

The discrepancies were described according to their sociodemographic, clinical, and microbiology features. The discrepancies were described as false positive (FP) if the expert labeled as consolidation the CXR and the system did not and false-negative (FN) if the expert labeled as other infiltrates/non-consolidation the CXR and the system as consolidation. In summary tables of continuous variables, interquartile ranges, and medians were assessed. Shapiro-Wilk test was performed to test normality. In summary tables of categorical variables, counts and percentages were used. Chi-squared and Fisher Tests (expected count ≥ 5) were performed when categorical variables. For continuous variables, Kruskal Wallis was performed. All hypothesis testing was carried out at the 5% significance level. All the analyses were performed using R software.

To test the adequacy and applicability of the SDT, the patterns found by the CNN ensemble were analyzed. To extract these patterns in a human-friendly way, XAI techniques were applied. Specifically, heatmaps were used to indicate the areas of the CRX where the system has found evidence that supports a particular diagnosis (consolidation — other infiltrates/non-consolidation) using the visualize cam function from the Keras vis package [30]. We used two output neurons to obtain a separate heatmap and generate the desired visualization for each of the two classes.

The adequacy of the model was tested by asking two pediatric infectious disease experts (PR and CM) if the pattern recognized as consolidation by the model in a subset of 40 CXR and pointed in the heatmap was a plausible consolidation pattern. The agreement was rated using a 0-5 Likert scale meaning 1: strongly disagree, 2: disagree, 3: Neutral, 4: Agree, and 5: Strongly agree.

The applicability of the model was tested using a subset of the training set (n=40) including 20 of CXRs classified as consolidation and 20 as non-consolidation. These 40 CRXs were randomly selected from the dataset of 190 chest x-rays. A total of three medicine interns in pediatrics classified the 40 CXRs. After that, they again classified these

Table 1: Summary descriptive table by performance

System*	Consolidation	Other infiltrates / no consolidation	p-value	Other infiltrates / no consolidation	Consolidation	p-value
Panel of experts**	Consolidation	Consolidation		Other infiltrates / no consolidation	Other infiltrates / no consolidation	
	N=106	N=18		N=39	N=13	
Gender:			0.539			0.309
Male	47 (44.3%)	6 (33.3%)		28 (71.8%)	7 (53.8%)	
Female	59 (55.7%)	12 (66.7%)		11 (28.2%)	6 (46.2%)	
Age (months):	40.6 [18.2;72.7]	28.7 [17.0;54.2]	0.338	20.0 [12.8;32.8]	31.5 [13.3;38.6]	0.665
Bacterial aetiology:			0.539			1.000
Yes	56 (52.8%)	6 (33.3%)		8 (20.5%)	2(15.4%)	
No	50 (55.7%)	12 (66.7%)		31 (79.5%)	11 (84.6%)	
Aetiology:			0.449			0.854
Atypical bacteria	34 (32.1%)	5 (27.8%)		5 (12.8%)	2 (15.4%)	
Typical bacteria	24 (22.6%)	2 (11.1%)		3 (7.69%)	0 (0.00%)	
Virus	48 (45.3%)	11 (61.1%)		31 (79.5%)	11 (84.6%)	
Complications:			0.153			0.561
No	76 (71.7%)	16 (88.9%)		35 (89.7%)	13 (100%)	
Yes	30 (28.3%)	2 (11.1%)		4 (10.3%)	0 (0.00%)	
PICU admission:			0.212			1.000
No	93 (87.7%)	18 (100%)		35 (89.7%)	13 (100%)	
Yes	13 (12.3%)	0 (0.00%)		4 (10.3%)	0 (0.00%)	

(*) System: CNNs deep learning algorithm.

(**) Panel of experts: two physicians and one radiologist

de-identified 40 CXRs (without knowing that they were the same) but using the decision-support tool, including the heatmaps. Any change of opinion after using the tool was analyzed. If this modification means an agreement with the panel experts we reported it as a success, if this modification means a disagreement with the panel of experts we reported it as a failure, and if no change of opinion we reported it as an agreement.

3 Results

3.1 Performance

A total of 190 CRXs images were used as a testing set to evaluate the SDT performance. Of those, 14/190 (7.4%) were excluded because the CXR was not crisp enough and the lung was not identifiable.

The CRXs were labeled by the panel of experts into consolidation (124/176, 70.4%) and no-consolidation/other infiltrates (52/176, 29.5%). A total of 31/176 (17.6%) discrepancies were found between the model and the panel of experts with a kappa index of 0.6. From those discrepancies, 18/176 (10.2%) were misclassified as other infiltrates/no-consolidation being FN. Of those, 3/18 (16.7%) raised doubts to some of the experts. A total of 13/176 (7.4%) were misclassified as consolidation being FP. The FN patients' features were like those classified as having consolidation in the CXR. Both FP and FN were mostly with viral etiology, and with no clinical complications. The discrepancies were summarized in Table 1.

The probability of consolidation predicted by the algorithm was slightly higher in the CXRs images that were classified as consolidation by both system and experts than the FP, however, these differences were not statistically significant (Figure 2). Likewise, the CXRs images that were classified as other infiltrates/no-consolidation presented no statistically significant differences with the FN.

Figure 2: Predicted probability of consolidation given by the system according to the agreement system-expert.*
 * TP: True positive (both classifications of CXRs as “consolidation”); FP: False Positive (classified by expert as “Other infiltrates/no pneumonia” and as consolidated by the System); TN: True Negative (both classifications of CXRs as “Other infiltrates/no pneumonia”); FN: False Negative (classified by expert as “consolidation” and as “Other infiltrates/no pneumonia” by the System)

The etiology according to the performance of the model was summarized in Figure 3. All the patients with typical bacteria such as *S. pneumoniae*, *S. pyogenes*, and *S. aureus* were equally classified by both system and expert physicians as having consolidated CXR. However, 2 patients with the atypical bacteria *M. pneumoniae* were FN. A total of 7/46 (15%) patients with an atypical bacterial etiology were discrepancies between the SDT and the expert, 5/47 (10.9%) were misclassified as other infiltrates, and only 2/47 (4.3%) were misclassified as consolidation. A total of 23/102 (22.6%) patients with a viral etiology were discrepancies between the SDT and the expert. 12/102 (11.8%) were misclassified as other infiltrates and 11/102 (10.8%) were misclassified as consolidation.

Overall, the SDT presented a balanced accuracy of 0.80 and an F1 score of 0.87. The area under the precision-recall curve of the model was 0.91 (Supplementary Figure 1). To perform the BLCA, the study population was divided according to age. A total of 134/176 (76%) were children below 5 years with a 64.9 (95% CI, 56.2-72.8) estimated prevalence of having consolidation in the CXR. The children older than 5 years old 42/176 (24%) presented a higher prevalence of having consolidation in the CXR (88.1 (95% CI, 73.6-95.5)). By the conventional method, which assumes that the interpretation by the panel of experts is 100% sensible and 100% specific, the sensitivity of the system reached 85.5 (95% CI, 77.8 - 90.9) and 75.0 (95% CI, 60.8-85.5) specificity. However, with BLCA, the sensitivity and specificity reached a median of 90.9 (95% Credible Interval (CrI), 81.2-99.9), and 77.7 (95% CrI, 63.3-98.1) respectively (Table 2). The BLCA model converges (Supplementary Figure 2, Supplementary Figure 3) and the fitness was acceptable with Bayesian posterior probability close to 0.5 (describing the observed data well [19]) (Supplementary Table 1).

Figure 3: Performance according to probable aetiology.*

* TTP: True positive (both classifications of CXRs as “consolidation”); FP: False Positive (classified by expert as “Other infiltrates/no pneumonia” and as consolidated by the System); TN: True Negative (both classifications of CXRs as “Other infiltrates/no pneumonia”); FN: False Negative (classified by expert as “consolidation” and as “Other infiltrates/no pneumonia” by the System)

3.2 Adequacy

The adequacy was tested by asking two senior physicians if they agree with the pattern observed and colored in the heatmap as consolidation by the System in 40 randomly selected CXRs. A total of 28/40 (70%) CXRs were rated as agree or strongly agree. Only 9/40 (22%) were classified as “strongly disagree”. An example of the heatmaps shown to the physicians is available in Figure 4.

3.3 Applicability

A total of 40 CXRs images were interpreted by three medical residents. These CXRs were interpreted with and without using the support decision system and the kappa index for the agreement was calculated. For the three residents, the interpretation using the SDT increased their agreement with the WHO experts panel in the validation set (Figure 5). All the residents found the tool useful and answered “yes” to the questions “Will you use it if finally implemented?” and “Do you feel confident to decide to use the tool?”.

Table 2: Diagnostic test performance subpopulations by age

Parameters	Physician assessment as a perfect gold standard (%)*	Bayesian latent class model (%)*
Prevalence of consolidation		
Patients \leq 5 years	64.9 (56.2 - 72.8)	60.2 (45.7 - 74.1)
Patients $>$ 5 years	88.1 (73.6 - 95.5)	85.0 (67.8 - 94.7)
Image read by physicians		
Sensitivity	100 (100 - 100)	98.6 (88.2 - 100)
Specificity	100 (100 - 100)	83.2 (60.7 - 99.9)
PPV	100 (100 - 100)	92.1 (76.0 - 100)
NPV	100 (100 - 100)	97.0 (71.2 - 100)
Deep learning		
Sensitivity	85.5 (77.8 - 90.9)	90.9 (81.2 - 99.9)
Specificity	75.0 (60.8 - 85.5)	77.7 (63.3 - 98.1)
PPV	89.1 (81.7 - 93.8)	88.7 (77.9 - 99.2)
NPV	68.4 (54.6 - 79.7)	81.5 (60.1 - 99.9)

* Conventional method assumed that the interpretation by the physicians is perfect (100% sensitivity and 100% specificity; all patients with gold standard test positive presented x-ray with consolidation and all patients with gold standard test negative presented x-ray with other infiltrates/no-pneumonia). Values shown are estimated means with 95% confidence interval

** Bayesian latent class model does not assume that any test is perfect. Values shown are estimated median with 95% credible interval. To cope with the unknown accuracy of the gold standard, variable “true” classification is included into the model. The variable “true” classification contains two mutually exclusive categories, “consolidation” or “other infiltrates”, and the real value of this variable for each subject is considered unobserved (i.e. latent). When the unobservable variable is categorical, the term “latent class analysis” applies. The chance that the test will be consolidation, if a subject has “consolidation” is the true sensitivity (Se), and the chance that the test will be other infiltrates if a subject is “other infiltrates” is true specificity (Sp). Therefore, this kind of model did not assume that any test is perfect, but consider true accuracy of each test for diagnosing the true classification (“consolidation” or “other infiltrates”).

Figure 4: Heatmaps of a consolidation sample 1. Left side, Neuron 0, shows the heatmaps for the non-consolidation class, whereas the right side, Neuron 1, shows the heatmaps for consolidation class for five individual CNNs.

4 discussion

This study has tested an automated support decision tool approach for the classification of CXRs into consolidation and other infiltrates/no consolidation according to WHO classification standardization. Upon pilot testing this tool, we found that it applied to medical residents, that it increased knowledge and decreased decisional conflicts.

Figure 5: Agreement between medical residents and experts before (yellow) and after (blue) using SDT

Images account for increasing amounts of medical data but require extensive manual interpretation. Providers need technologies to aid them in extracting, visualizing, and interpreting them. The radiological examination plays an important role in the diagnosis of CAP and treatment decisions [33]. However, there is a higher subjectivity and higher inter and intraobserver variability in the interpretation of CXRs [34–36]. Recently, several artificial intelligence (AI) algorithms have emerged to offer assistance in interpretation [37–39]. However, the evaluation methodology used for assessing these algorithms only used popular metrics such as the area under the curve (AUC), or F-scores for label-based precision and recall evaluations. In this study, we further evaluated the tool for clinical purposes based on sensitivity, specificity, and clinical predictive value rather than label-based evaluations. This tool presented high sensitivity and high specificity compared with the routine CXRs interpretation made by the attending physician. Importantly, there were only 2 patients with a typical bacterial etiology where the SDT yield discrepant results according to the expert, and none of them were driven by *S.pneumoniae*. In other words, none of the FN was critical (with clinical complications of PICU admitted).

The evaluation of new diagnostic tools usually relied on a perfect ground truth/gold standard, which is obtained by a loose consensus process such as a majority vote from a few board-certified radiologists/expert physicians. However, if the error rates of a gold standard are ignored during the evaluation of new diagnostic tests or tools, the accuracy of these new systems can be underestimated, and the prevalence can be either under- or over-estimated. In this study, we have evaluated the performance using a Bayesian latent analysis allowing us to provide a better estimate accounting for this interpretation variability [19, 29, 31].

The generation and evaluation of a model follow the step of training, validation, and testing. The training procedure is defined as the design and fit of the ML model using a training set. On the other side, the validation and testing steps are usually interchanged in the literature, defined as a process of evaluation of the model [32]. However, the validation step is often used for the model tune and hypothesis testing, interfering with the final model selection, and possibly adding some bias to the results. The testing process, on the contrary, is an unbiased evaluation of the performance of the final model in real conditions. We have performed a testing step based on XAI techniques to evaluate the adequacy

of the model and the applicability for the target users. Overall, senior physicians evaluated the ability of the system to identify logical patterns rating correctly the majority of the CXRs labeled as consolidation. On the other hand, the results of the questionnaire study show that most of the resident respondents liked using the tool and feel confident using it in their clinical duties. This tool drove them to a better decision according to the interpretation by WHO panel experts.

This study has several limitations. First, the assessment of the tool's impact on knowledge and decisional conflict is limited by the fact that there was no control group comparing usual care to use of the tool, but the pre-and post-results were encouraging. This is, to our knowledge, the first AI product specifically aimed at the diagnosis of pneumonia in the pediatric population. Second, this is a pilot testing study but further testing in several scenarios as low-income countries should be tested. Third, more senior experts and medical experts are needed for inferring better quality controls in applicability and adequacy and refining the system image segmentation. Third, the images were collected from the clinical practice and not specifically for research purposes. These images are sometimes blurred or with low contrast because the median age of the patients was 2 years, and it is difficult to have good quality images in this population. For this reason, a total of 14 images were discarded due to the bad quality of the image

The development of these tools requires a coordinated effort. This work shows that it takes a multidisciplinary team effort where physicians, data managers, machine learning researchers, medical imaging specialists, software developers, and statisticians all need to work together to do a systematic end-to-end study, design, and execution. Further research is required to assess the clinical acceptance of artificial intelligence in the real world and quantify the benefit of such automation to physicians and their patients.

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